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“OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARIDA TIL VA USLUB MASALASI: TAHLIL, TASNIF, QIYOS”

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OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARIDA TIL VA USLUB MASALASI: TAHLIL, TASNIF, QIYOS

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OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARIDA TIL VA USLUB

MASALASI: TAHLIL, TASNIF, QIYOS

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THE ISSUE OF LANGUAGE AND STYLE IN THE MEDIA:

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Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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ПРОБЛЕМА ЯЗЫКА И СТИЛЯ В СМИ: АНАЛИЗ,

КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ, СРАВНЕНИЕ

Ташкент, Узбекистан

To'plamdan medialingvistikaning dolzarb masalalari, mediamatnlarning ta'sirchanligini oshirish yo'llari, noshirlik sohasini rivojlantirishning istiqbolli yo'nalishlariga oid yangiliklar, adabiyotshunoslik masalalari, tarjima mahorati, innovatsion g'oyalar va texnologiyalar, o'zbek tilining sohada qo'llanilishi, OAV matnlarining tili, uslubi va tahriri sohasida mavjud muammolarga bag'ishlangan maqolalar o'rin olgan. Undan mazkur sohada ilmiy tadqiqot olib borayotgan olimlar, tadqiqotchilar, magistrant va talabalar foydalanishi mumkin, shuningdek, ommaviy axborot vositalarida til va uslub muammolarining yechimini izlash, tahlil, tasnif va qiyos asosida tegishli xulosalar chiqarish va tavsiyalar berishda ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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LEARNING TOGETHER EACH OTHER'S LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The author presents the language learning technique through his life experiences in this thesis. He also explains his reasons for learning world languages : English, Spanish, French, and Uzbek.*

Keywords: language learning, education, school, methodology, student, pupil

Since officially September this year, I have lived here in Tashkent. My wife is Uzbek, and we live with her mom and our cat, Miya, in a neighborhood considered part of the center. I have taught French at the Alliance Française since last Spring and have worked at Profi University since mid-October as Deputy Head of the Tourism Department. Behind this bombastic title, my occupation consists of acting as an Academic Coordinator to ensure that the double degree program we are developing with a French higher school of tourism is compliant with our mutual commitments and the regulations to which we are subject, as well as to advice and accompany students regarding the exchange year some of them will accomplish in their fourth academic year.

Before September, I had come several times to Uzbekistan. The first was a week ago, in November 2018, in Buxoro – Samarqand – Toshkent. I was invited to have a plov at a local family's through an online accommodation platform. At the end of the dinner, I was warmly invited to return to your country, which I did a few months later, in April 2019. The daughter of the house and I confessed our mutual feelings. However, it was not before last year that I returned to Uzbekistan, and we married only this year, in Spring. The pandemic has passed by, and so have episodes of our complicated lives. Adversity on a global and personal scale made us stronger and made our love grow. Moreover, we are now married and living together here after all we have been through. As a binational and bicultural couple, it is, if not natural, logical that we start learning each other's language.

It would be fairer if my wife were here this morning to tell you this story instead of me since she is much more gifted in languages than I am. As she has family obligations and trusts me to tell you about our mutual apprenticeship, I will do my best. Above all, we come from different linguistic backgrounds. She is Uzbek. She was born at the very end of the Soviet Union, but the primary language spoken at the family table was Russian. Uzbek is her mother language, but she knows Russian even better. Since her mother is an English teacher, my wife also has excellent proficiency in this language, which we mostly use to communicate. I am French, and though I have lived in seven countries before coming here, I can only speak, besides my mother language, a passable English and a slightly more convincing Italian, with a proficiency in the latter two languages equal to a C1 level. My wife's English, as her mother's and as the English of many Uzbek speakers, is influenced by American English, while mine is more imbued with the European roots of Dusty Springfield's language.

For historical reasons dating back to the conquest by William of Normandy, English is made of 29% words of French origin (en.wikipedia.org, 2024) and an

additional 29% words of Latin or another romance language, which makes it easier for me – I studied Latin in middle school – to make it mine. It is not the case for most of my fellow citizens, whose reputation for being reluctant to speak English is well established. In 2023, French people were the 43rd in the world in terms of English proficiency (en.wikipedia.org, 2024), on a par with Cuba, and well behind Benelux, Nordics, German-speaking, Baltic countries, but also Croatia, Greece, Poland, Bulgaria, Hungary, Slovakia, Serbia, Czechia, Moldova, Albania, and all the European romance language countries, namely Portugal, Romania, Italy and Spain. Are we that bad at English and foreign languages? Or are we just reluctant to speak the nowadays uncontested *lingua franca mundi*, a status once ours? Could it be jealousy?

In a globalized world, knowing English is mandatory to feel like a fish in the water. So why bother learning other languages? Why did I learn Italian starting in middle school? Most French pupils have the choice between only German and Spanish as a second foreign language, but, being in a region bordering Italy, I could choose Italian. I remember I was offered to learn German, as I had good grades and German is considered difficult, attracting the best students regardless of their interest in the language and its cultures (with an "s" because, across time, Germany and Austria have developed specific and different cultures within the European civilization). Spanish? I never considered this option. Spanish came later: it is easy to read, and its rules are less tricky than French. My mother briefly lived in Rome at a young age. Her family had friends in Turin, a few hour's drive from home, and we spent a lot of Sundays there when I was a child. However, I mostly remember I insisted then on the ease of learning Italian, even saying it would save me a lot of painful working hours – I was lazy and proud of it. I was 12, and I had the right to be lazy. If later I happened to briefly regret not having learned German (after falling in love with Wien), I never regretted being lazy because Italian is easy for a French

speaker and unspeakably (and subjectively) beautiful. Its melody is reflected in the opera and the music *leggera – dalla Scala a San Remo*, and the country, with its mountains, monuments, and coasts, shows an unequaled variety of landscapes, climates, and terroirs. Italian is for my *piacere e felicità*. If English is mandatory, Italian, for me, is necessary.

My wife learned Russian, which was spoken at home, along with Uzbek. She also learned English at school and took advantage of her mother's profession as an English teacher. Since October, she has been learning French at the Alliance Française, where I teach twice weekly. I have also started learning Russian, as the Alliance Française provides its native French teachers with such courses. Why not use Uzbek, which is the country's only official language? Uzbekistan's language policy is not the topic here; I will leave it aside and keep it for another statement when I know more about this fascinating subject.

My wife is learning French at an A1 level as a beginner, twice two hours a week, with an Uzbek teacher trained to teach beginners. Being a French teacher and a native, I do not consider myself, for the moment, ready to teach beginners because it requires pedagogic skills I do not have now. This is why I rejected several offers to teach French to beginners, and I am convinced that, natively or not, teaching to beginners is severe. My Uzbek colleagues at the Alliance Française or Profi University do it much better than I would. However, when we review the lessons with my wife, with the notebook and the notes she takes, it is inspiring, and I can measure how accurate the notebook is, how good the teacher is, and how outstanding the student is.

My Russian lessons are given by a fellow Alliance Française teacher, a Uzbek woman who speaks fluent Russian and is very lovely, understanding, and patient. Unfortunately, our material is not as good as the one given to my wife and her fellow students. Moreover, my hectic professional rhythm does not always make it possible

for me to attend the lessons. So, my wife is much more advanced in French than I am in Russian, and it would be relatively more straightforward now to have a conversation together in French than in Russian. However, we had the idea to use the notes taken during her courses to enhance my Russian vocabulary. She would show me what she did, and I would apply the notions and vocabulary she learned to Russian. It would produce a booklet with words in French, Russian, and even Uzbek, loosely based on the Guide parlé français-Uzbek-russe she found at home and gave me—a precious resource.

Another idea, quite conventional at first sight, would be to take note of everything in our environment, starting with home. From the apartment's front door, we would list every item from the floor to the ceiling and name them in French, Russian, and Uzbek (FRUZ). We would also list every item in the furniture, mostly a big wardrobe and cupboard, where we store Miya's food, among other tMiya's. We would then apply the same method to the other rooms.

In the hallway, for example, there is a doormat, a plate for Miya, a water fountain, a shoe rack, a wardrobe, a bench, a coffee table, two frames on the wall, and various commuturs. В коридоре, например, есть коврик, посуда для Мии, фонтанчик для воды для Мии, полка для обуви, шкаф, скамейка, журнальный столик, две рамки на стене, различные выключатели. Masalan, koridorda gilam, Miya uchun plastinka, Miya uchun suv favvorasi, poyabzal uchun javon, shkaf, skameyka, kofe stoli, devordagi ikkita ramka, turli xil kalitlar mavjud. Now that we have spent a few weeks each learning the other's message, we feel a bit more confident. Mind you, this statement in front of you this morning may act as a motivating element to implement what I have just described.

For this reason, and also because I was in another life a journalist, and I am now working in Toshkent in higher education, I would like to thank the Ministry of Higher Education, Sciences and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the

Journalism and Mass Communications the University of Uzbekistan, for letting me today share a small quantity of my experience in your country, a country for which, as for my wife, my love is growing every day. Sizga katta rahmat!

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BIRGALIKDA BIR-BIRINING TILINI O'RGANISH

Amauri CHARVÍ-DUFUR

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezisda muallif til o'rganish texnikasini hayotiy tajribalari orqali ifodalab bergan. Unda dunyo tillari – ingliz tili, ispan tili, fransuz tili hamda o'zbek tillarini o'rganish sabablari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: til o'rganish, ta'lim, maktab, metodika, talaba, o'quvchi

O'SMIR YOSHIDAGI O'QUVCHILARNING ESTETIK TARBIYA ASPEKTIDA MILLIY MADANIYATINING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada muallif o'smir yoshidagi maktab o'quvchilarining estetik tarbiyasida umumtalim maktablarida ijtimoiy fanlar o'qituvchilarining olib borayotgan darslari va sinfdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarning o'ni haqida o'z qarashlari bilan o'rtoqlashgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: maktab o'quvchilari, madaniy meroslar, urf-odatlar, hunarmandchilik, badiiy adabiyot.

Kirish

XXI asr boshlarida insoniyat tarixi yangi bosqichga o'tdi, bu millatlararo chegaralarning ma'lum darajada yo'q qilinishi, iqtisodiyotning globallashuvi va madaniy an'analarning birlashishi bilan tavsiflanadi (Elmandjra M., 1990). Bu, o'z navbatida, milliy madaniyatlarning etnik o'ziga xosligi va janrlari xilma-xilligiga e'tiborning kuchayishiga sabab bo'lmoqda (Quan, C. & et. al., 2022).

O'zbek xalqi qadimiy tarixga, boy madaniyatga, go'zal urf-odat va an'analarga ega (Xoliqova R.E., 2020). So'nggi 40 yillikda sodir bo'lgan fojia moddiy madaniyat

yodgorliklariga, millatning psixologik holati va salomatligiga ulkan zarar yetkazgan bo'lsa-da, xalqning ruhiyatini sindira olmadi, uning ma'naviy madaniyati rivojini kechiktirmadi. Shubhasiz, hech qanday milliy madaniyat o'z-o'zidan yopiq, tashqi ta'sirlardan ajralgan holda qolmasligi kerak (Karaganis J., 2001). Shunga qaramay, boshqa xalqlar, xususan, O'zbekiston xalqlari badiiy yutuqlarini faol o'zlashtirib, muvaffaqiyatli qayta ishlayotgan o'zbek xalqi madaniyati hech qachon o'zining an'anaviy o'ziga xosligi va milliy jilosini yo'qotmagan.

An'analarni saqlash va yo'qotmaslik, o'zgaruvchan moda, qattiq bozor va bozor talablari ta'sirida umumiy ommaga tarqalib ketmaslik – bugungi kunda har qanday darajadagi madaniyat arboblarning asosiy vazifalari (Mohammad Kh. & Panarina E., 2017).

Metod

O'zbek xalqining milliy badiiy madaniyati o'ziga xos va noyobdir. Uning poydevori asrlar davomida o'tgan avlodlar madaniy tajribasini o'zida muttasil yangicha mazmun, yangi g'oyalar bilan to'ldirib kelayotgan xalqning ma'naviy o'zligini anglashning hayotbaxsh tomirlaridan oziqlanadi. U har qanday madaniyat singari, ma'lum darajada universal bo'lib, boshqa xalqlar madaniyati bilan turli xil aloqalarda mavjud va rivojlanadi. Bu aloqalar orqali turli xalqlar madaniyatining o'zaro boyishi va o'zaro ta'siri, ma'lum madaniy arxetiplarning shakllanishi, madaniy o'zaro ta'sirning intensivligi va davomiyligi holatida esa milliy va konfessionallardan yuqori xususiyatga ega bo'lgan madaniy jamoalarning shakllanishi sodir bo'ladi (Казакова Д.Г., 2016).

“Madaniyatning umumbashariyligi, – deb ta'kidlaydi V.M. Jirmunskiy , – xalqning boshqa xalqlar, ayniqsa qo'shni xalqlar bilan umumiy muloqot va madaniy aloqa tilini topishga, ko'p millatli davlatning madaniy spektridagi o'rnini topishga imkon beradi. Xalqning madaniy yakkalanishi uning madaniyatining tanazzulga

uchrashiga, o'zligini yo'qotishiga – madaniy assimilyatsiyaga olib keladi” (Жирмунский В.М., 2009).

Bugungi kunda O'zbekistonda milliy madaniyatning tiklanishi jamiyatning birlashishini va respublikaning madaniy-tarixiy merosi rivojlanib borayotganiga ishonchni taqozo etadi. Respublikamizda tinchlik va ijtimoiy totuvlikka erishish, o'tmish va bugunni anglash, O'zbekiston Respublikasida madaniyatni rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlarini tanlash maqsadida hozirdanoq maqsadli ma'rifiy ishlar olib borilmoqda.

O'tgan asrning 80-yillari oxiridagi inqiroz respublikada katta tanazzulga olib keldi. Ko'plab madaniy qadriyatlar yo'q bo'layozdi, ilgari ta'lim, fan va madaniyat faoliyatini ta'minlagan moddiy va moliyaviy baza kcuhsizlanib qoldi. Bu respublikada madaniy halokatga olib keldi. Shuning uchun ham mustaqillik yillarida O'zbekistonda istiqomat qiluvchi o'zbek va boshqa xalqlarning madaniy merosini tiklash va rivojlantirish muammosi paydo bo'ldi (Турсунов И.Н., 1997).

Tadqiqotchilarning ta'kidlashicha, haqiqiy o'zbeklar shaxsiy erkinlik, tenglik, or-nomus kabi yuksak tushunchalarni qadrlaydi.

Bu borada rus etnologi Yan Chesnovning quyidagi so'zlarini eslash bejiz emas: “O'zbeklar Markaziy Osiyoda ma'naviy izlanishlar markazini yaratgan o'sha qadimiy tamaddun vorislari ekanligi aniqlandi. S. Yesenin mehribonlik va kechirimlilik insoniyatning mutafakkirlar, rahnamolar tushunchasi emas, balki uning do'sti, oddiy o'zbek maktabi o'qituvchisi Abduhakim Turg'unov kabi sodda insonning hayot yo'li bo'lishi mumkinligini anglagan (БУЭ, 1985).

Ko'p millatli mamlakatimiz xalqlarining har birining tarixiy ildizlariga, butun ma'naviy qadriyatlariga murojaat qilmasdan turib, ma'naviyatni tiklash, an'anaviy xalq axloqini uyg'otish mumkin emas. Shu munosabat bilan barcha xalqlarning ma'naviy muhitini tubdan o'zgartirish, madaniyatini qayta tiklash, yo'qolgan yuksak ma'naviyatni tiklash zarurati har qachongidan ham dolzarb bo'lib qoldi.

Xalq qo'shiqlari O'zbekiston xalqlari umumiy tarixining yangi qatlamlarini ochish va tushunish imkonini beradi. Bu tarixiy davrda xalqning etnik-tarixiy xususiyatlarini, madaniyatining boshqa shakllarining (mehnat madaniyati, badiiy madaniyati, turmush madaniyati va axloqi) o'ziga xosligini rasmiylashtirish jarayonlari jadal rivojlandi va yakunlandi. O'zbek xalqining badiiy tafakkurida hayotni ajoyib tarzda umumlashtirilgan idrok etishdan moddiy va badiiy madaniyatning ulug'vor yodgorliklarini yaratish, voqelik muammolarini tahlil qilish va tushunishgacha bo'lgan katta sakrash bo'ldi.

O'tgan XX-asrda uning madaniyatining yangi shakllari paydo bo'ldi, ular yuqori rivojlanish darajasiga ko'tarildi. O'zbeklarning badiiy adabiyoti, professional musiqasi, rasmlari va grafik asarlari nafaqat Markaziy Osiyoda, balki ko'plab mamlakatlarda ham mashhur.

O'zbekiston milliy badiiy madaniyatining ko'zga ko'ringan namoyandasi SSSR xalq artisti Tamaraxonimdir. Raqqosa, qo'shiqchi, aktrisa va xoreograf (asl ismi Tamara Artemovna Petrosyan) 1906 yil 29 martda Yangi Marg'ilonda (hozirgi Farg'ona, O'zbekiston) kamtarin arman oilasida tug'ilgan. U xoreograf va ajoyib ijrochi sifatida o'zbek raqslarining bir qancha yangi ko'rinishlarini yaratdi. Tamaraxonim qayerda bo'lmasin, o'z konsert dasturini o'zbek "Lazgi"si bilan boshlagan, ona yurtining go'zal go'shasiga farzandlik mehrini berdi.

Tamaraxonim o'zbek ayollari raqsi ijro uslubini isloh qilgan, jahon xalqlarining qo'shiq va raqs folklorini o'rgangan, qo'shiq va raqs miniatyura janrini yaratgan buyuk san'atkor. Uning "SSSR xalqlarining qo'shiqlari va raqslari" va "Dunyo xalqlarining qo'shiqlari va raqslari" dasturlarida 86 tilda 500 dan ortiq qo'shiqlar, xoreografik kompozitsiyalar va dunyoning ko'plab xalqlarining raqslari mavjud (BYƏ, 1985).

Ijro san'ati o'zining ayniqsa ifodali yuz ifodalari va imo-ishoralari ("qo'shiqlar") bilan ajralib turardi. U o'zbek raqslari etdi "Kataugon", "Qori navo",

“Keshayun”, “Xorazm syuitasi”, “Dil hiroj” va boshqalarni yuksak did bilan ijro etoldi. Tamaraxonim E. G. Brusilovskiyning birinchi o‘zbek baleti “Gulandom” librettosini yaratishda ishtirok etgan. U o‘zining raqslarni o‘zi sahnalashtirgan ajoyib ijrochi edi.

Tamaraxonim Butunjahon dekarativ san’ati ko‘rgazmasida (Parij, 1925) o‘zbek san’atini birinchilardan bo‘lib xorijda namoyish etdi. 1935 yilda u 1-Jahon xalq raqslari festivali ishtirokchisi sifatida o‘zbek xalq raqslarini jahonga namoyish etadi.

U sobiq SSSR, O‘zbekiston va jahon xalqlari raqslarini keng targ‘ib qildi, turli millatlar, ularning madaniyatini yaqinlashtirish va o‘zaro boyitish, odamlarni bir oiladek do‘stlik, birodarlik ruhida tarbiyalashga xizmat qildi va shu orqali jahon san’ati xazinasiga o‘z hissasini qo‘shildi. San’atkor o‘z ijodi repertuariga dunyoning deyarli barcha xalqlarining raqslarini kiritdi.

O‘zbek mumtoz adabiyotining asoschilaridan biri, “O‘tkan kunlar” romani bilan jahon adabiyoti hazinasiga o‘lkan hissa qo‘shgan ijodkor, yorqin iste’dod sohibi A.Qodiriy nomini alohida ta’kidlab o‘tish joiz. Bu insonning fe’l-atvorini, irodasini, adolat va haqiqatga intilishini, Vatanga, o‘z xalqiga bo‘lgan chuqur mehrini hech narsa sindira olmadi. U millatning vijdoni edi. A.Qodiriy o‘z asarlarida qon to‘kilishini tubdan qoralab, A.Navoiyning hech qachon qurol bilan hech qanday muammoni hal qilmaslik ahdini o‘quvchilarga eslatdi. A.Qodiriy asarlarining YUNESKO oltin fondidan joy olishi uning asrning buyuk adiblaridan biri ekanligini ko‘rsatadi.

O‘zbek xalq og‘zaki ijodini birinchilardan bo‘lib tadqiq etgan, o‘zbek xalq folklorining asoschisi Hodi Zarif nomi O‘zbekiston tarixida mangu qoladi. Olim O‘zbekiston va O‘rta Osiyo davlatlari bo‘ylab folklor ekspeditsiyalarini uyushtirib, juda ko‘p xalq og‘zaki ijodi durdonalarini yig‘di va ularni tadqiq etib, nashr qildi. Olimning xalqimiz oldidagi buyuk xizmatlari uchun u davlat mukofoti va bir qancha orden-medallar bilan taqdirlandi.

Maktab o'quvchilarini milliy madaniyat vositalaridan foydalangan holda estetik tarbiyalash o'quvchilarning estetik ongni shakllantirishga qaratilgan bo'lib, uning yordamida insonning estetik madaniyati baholanadi. Asosiy vosita – bu estetik idealdir. Maktabda ular madaniy tadbirlarda o'zbek xalq ertaklari, dostonlari va qo'shiqlarining qahramonlari bo'lishlari mumkin.

O'zbek madaniyati sivilizatsiyalashgan xalqlar madaniyatiga xos bo'lgan barcha tur va janrlarni ifodalaydi. Shu bilan birga, uning geografik joylashuvi, diniy xususiyatlari va etnik-madaniy muhiti bilan belgilanadigan ma'lum bir etnik o'ziga xoslik mavjud.

Ko'pmillatli O'zbekiston Respublikasi xalqi badiiy hunarmandchiligining o'ziga xos rang-barangligi bilan ajralib turadi. Ularning har biri mahsulot ishlab chiqarish uchun maxsus texnika va texnologiyaga ega, o'ziga xos kompozitsion va estetik naqshlarga, obyektini ishlab chiqarishning amaliy texnologiyasiga qo'yiladigan talablarga, ma'lum bir material bilan ishlashga: metall, yog'och, loy va boshqalarga amal qiladi.

Xalq amaliy san'ati metall buyumlar, jumladan, pichoqli qurollar dizaynida ham yorqin ifodalangan. XIX-asrning ikkinchi yarmidan boshlab o'zbeklar uchun an'anaviy qirrali qurollar tobora yorqin dekorativ xususiyatga ega bo'ldi. Jumladan, xanjarlar yengil va nafis bo'lib, pichoqlarni badiiy qayta ishlash, dastasini bezashga alohida e'tibor beriladi. Shunday qilib, shox yoki suyakdan yasalgan tutqichlar endi yaltiroq va boy bezaklar bilan qoplangan va yog'och qini qimmatbaho marokash bilan qoplangan va qo'shimcha ravishda kumush plitalar bilan bezatilgan.

Tasviriy san'at o'qituvchisi o'quvchilarni asosiy texnik usullar va mahsulotlarning eng yaxshi badiiy echimini topish usullari bilan tanishtirishi, ma'lum bir materialning eng xarakterli ekspressiv imkoniyatlarini, amaliy ishning asosiy usullarini, metall qotishmasining texnologiyasi va tamoyillarini aniqlashi va

ko'rsatishi kerak; ta'lim ijodiy ishining yakuniy natijasining asosiy maqsadini doimo ta'kidlab turadi.

O'zbekistonda yog'ochdan yasalgan badiiy hunarmandchilik, ayniqsa, keng tarqalgan. Bundan tashqari, qadim zamonlardan beri yog'ochga ishlov berish xalq hunarmandchiligining eng keng tarqalgan turlaridan biri bo'lib kelgan. Shu bilan birga, o'zbek hunarmandlari turli xil yog'ochga ishlov berish va stanoklardan, shu jumladan, oqadigan suvdan foydalangan holda mexanik qurilmalar – charxpalak va tegirmonlar qurganligi xalq hunarmandchiligining rivoj topganidan dalolat beradi.

O'zbek hunarmandlari hozirda metall o'ymakorligiga alohida e'tibor qaratib, qirrali qurollardan tortib to uy-ro'zg'or buyumlarigacha bo'lgan deyarli barcha metall buyumlarni gul yoki nuqtali bezaklar bilan qoplaydi. Shu bilan birga, o'zbeklar orasida islomgacha bo'lgan davrdan ma'lum bo'lgan quyosh belgilaridan bezaklari sifatida keng foydalanilgani o'z-o'zidan o'zbek amaliy san'atining ajoyib davomiyligidan dalolat beradi. Bundan tashqari, o'zbek zargarlari o'z mahsulotlarini bezashda an'anaviy naqshlardan foydalanishga ham murojaat qilganlar, ular po'latni tilla bilan o'yib, zardo'zlash yo'li bilan buyumlar yasaganlar (Шафрин С.А., 2019).

An'anaviy naqshlar toshni qayta ishlashda ham keng qo'llaniladi, masalan, an'anaviy tosh qabr toshlarini ishlab chiqarishda. Biroq amaliy san'atning bu turida an'anaviy o'zbek ornamenti asta-sekin arab yozuviga almashtirildi. Shu bilan birga, an'anaviy naqsh turli xil jun mahsulotlarida saqlanib qolgan, masalan, o'zbeklar uchun an'anaviy bo'lgan jun va kigiz gilamlari turli xil va rang-barang naqshlar bilan qoplangan. Eng ko'p ishlatiladigan ranglar yorqin sariq, to'q sariq, qizil, yashil, qora va ko'k edi. Umuman olganda, o'zbek gilamlarining rang sxemasi yorqin, quyosh, yarim oy, yulduzlar, o'simlik va hayvonot naqshlarining ramziy tasvirlari asosida yaratilgan bezak oddiy, qat'iy shaklga ega bo'lgan.

Ayniqsa, maktabga o'qishga qadam qo'yganga qadar o'quvchilar gilamdo'zlikning asosiy hunari gilamdo'zlik bo'lgan joylarda o'sgan o'quvchilar

rang massalari va dog'lar o'zaro bog'liqligini juda nozik va aniq his etishlari, oson o'zlashtirib olishlari va ko'paytirishlari, geometrik, gulli naqshlar namunalarini yaratishlarini alohida ta'kidlash zarur. Ular o'qituvchi tomonidan taklif qilingan deyarli har qanday obrazli motivni an'anaviy "gilam tiliga" tarjima qiladilar, hatto "gilam" bezaklarining an'anaviy qonunlariga ko'ra nisbatan murakkab kompozitsion elementlar to'plamini hal qilishadi.

Tasviriy va bezak san'ati o'qitish tarixini o'z taraqqiyotining turli bosqichlarida tahlil qilib, shunday xulosaga kelamizki, u hamma davrlarda ham o'tmish tajribasiga, xalqning shakllangan badiiy-pedagogik estetik an'alarini o'zlashtirish va ulardan foydalanishga asoslangan. Umumta'lim maktablarida tasviriy va bezak san'atini o'qitishning hozirgi bosqichida ham bu qoida eskirgan emas.

Tasviriy va dekorativ san'atni o'rgatish bo'yicha tarixan shakllangan xalq tajribasining ahamiyati shundaki, u asrlar davomida rivojlanib brogan, u amaliyotda sinovdan o'tgan, va bu, o'z navbatida, eng muvaffaqiyatli namunalarni aniqlash imkonini bergan.

Milliy badiiy an'analardan mohirona foydalanish o'qituvchiga nafaqat o'quvchilarning mavjud badiiy va ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish, balki ularni milliy badiiy madaniyat qadriyatlarini bilan tanishtirish imkonini beradi.

Yuqoridagilarni umumlashtirib, xulosa qilishimiz mumkinki, o'zbeklar uchun yoshlar va maktab o'quvchilarini tarbiyalash va tarbiyalashning eng samarali shakli milliy badiiy madaniyat – madaniy, axloqiy, badiiy va estetik qadriyatlardan foydalanadigan asosdir. Binobarin, yosh avlodni estetik-badiiy tarbiyalashda eng muhim narsa o'quvchilarda ajdodlarining axloqiy-estetik merosiga qiziqish va hurmatga erishishdir. U ko'p jihatdan badiiy ijodda, hunarmandchilikda, o'ziga xos texnikada va bezak naqshlarida mujassamlangan. Bu zamonaviy maktabda estetik tarbiya binosi qurilishi kerak bo'lgan bobo va otalar tomonidan qo'yilgan poydevordir.

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THE PLACE OF NATIONAL-ARTISTIC CULTURE IN THE ASPECT OF AESTHETIC EDUCATION OF ADOLESCENT STUDENTS

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Annotation: *In this article, the author shares his views on the role of lessons and extracurricular activities conducted by social science teachers in secondary schools in the aesthetic education of adolescent schoolchildren.*

Keywords: schoolchildren, cultural heritage, traditions, crafts, fiction.

MADANIYATLARARO MUNOSABATLARNING RIVOJLANISHI TENDENTSIYALARI

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tezisda mualliflar jamiyat taraqqiyotida madaniyatlararo munosabatlarning rivojlanishi omillari to'xtalib o'tib, bu boradagi qilinishi kerak bo'lgan ishlarga o'z munosabatlarini bildirgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyatlararo muloqot; til va madaniyatning o'zaro ta'siri; til va madaniyat funksiyalari; til va madaniyat o'zaro ta'sirining siyosiy belgilari.

Kirish

Ijtimoiy munosabatlar inson hayotining barcha jabhalarida rivojlanadi. Ular odatda siyosiy, iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy guruhlariga bo'linadi. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, so'zning keng ma'nosida madaniyat tushunchasi inson faoliyatining fiziologik, moddiy va ma'naviy barcha sohalarini qamrab oladi. Biroq, bunda tilning madaniyatning ma'naviy shakli bilan o'zaro ta'siri, ya'ni madaniyatning an'analar,

urf-odatlar, axloq va boshqalar shaklida ifodalanishi tushuniladi. Bu sohalar orasida tilning madaniyatning ma'naviy shakli bilan o'zaro ta'siri alohida ahamiyatga ega. Bu yerda til va madaniyatning o'zaro ta'siri mazmuni deganda shaxslar o'rtasidagi muloqot jarayonining tili bo'yicha xizmat tushunilishi kerak, ikkinchisi esa, ijtimoiy mavqega ko'ra, oddiy fuqarolar yoki nodavlat tashkilotlari va davlat organlari vakillari madaniyat sohasidagi ijtimoiy munosabatlar jarayonida yuzaga keladigan turli milliy madaniy shaxslarga tegishli bo'lishi mumkin. Bu shuni anglatadiki, til orqali muloqotga madaniyatlarning o'zlari emas, balki tegishli madaniyatlar o'ziga xos semantik va ramziy chegaralarni belgilaydigan odamlar kiradi. Natijada, birinchidan, boy madaniyat o'zida boshqa madaniyatga semantik ko'prik qurish imkonini beradigan ko'plab yashirin imkoniyatlarni o'z ichiga oladi; ikkinchidan, ijodkor inson asl madaniyat tomonidan qo'yilgan cheklovlardan tashqariga chiqadi. Shunday ekan, inson madaniyat yaratuvchisi bo'lgan holda turli madaniyatlar o'rtasidagi muloqot yo'lini topa oladi [1,24].

Bundan kelib chiqib, an'ana va urf-odatlar me'yorlari ijtimoiy munosabatlarni tartibga solib turishi munosabati bilan aytish mumkinki, madaniyat tildan farqli o'laroq, o'rnatish funksiyalarini bajaradi, ya'ni jamiyatda ijtimoiy munosabatlarni vujudga keltiradi, til esa madaniyatga nisbatan o'ziga xos xususiyatga ega, ya'ni xizmat ko'rsatish funktsiyalari, aloqaning zarur sharti bo'lib xizmat qiladi va u orqali ijtimoiy munosabatlarning paydo bo'lishi, o'zgarishi va to'xtashini ta'minlaydi.

Madaniyatlararo munosabatlarning rivojlanishidagi ushbu tendentsiya madaniyatlararo muloqot omillarini, jumladan, til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sir muammosini uchta asosiy pozitsiyadan ko'rib chiqish zaruriyatiga olib keladi: birinchidan, til va madaniyatning bir xil milliy-davlat sub'ekti doirasidagi o'zaro ta'siri; lekin turli milliy-madaniy xususiyatlarga ega; ikkinchidan, yagona davlat tiliga ega bo'lgan bir davlat doirasida turli millat va elatlarning tili va madaniyatining

o'zaro ta'siri; uchinchi, turli xalqlar tili va madaniyatining bir-biri bilan o'zaro ta'siri.

Masalan, birinchi holatda O'zbekiston misolida o'zbek va qoraqalpoq tillari va madaniyatlarining o'zaro ta'siri xizmat qilishi mumkin [2,18-23]; ikkinchi holat, Rossiya misolida, rus federal davlat tili mavjud bo'lganda, aytaylik, Buryatiya, Dog'iston, Ingushetiya kabi milliy davlat tuzilmalari milliy tillari va madaniyatlarining o'zaro ta'sirini o'z ichiga oladi; Uchinchi misol – har biri milliy-davlat suverenitetiga ega bo'lgan O'zbekiston, Rossiya va Buyuk Britaniya xalqlari tillari va madaniyatlarining o'zaro ta'siri. Bu yerda, agar birinchi ikkita pozitsiya ko'proq ma'lum va tushunarli bo'lsa, uchinchi pozitsiya ko'p jihatdan yangi va faol rivojlanib, til va madaniyatning o'zaro ta'sirini universallashtirish yo'nalishiga o'zgartirishga ta'siri kuchayishi bilan. Bunday universallashtirish tendentsiyasi tilning va u orqali turli xalqlar madaniyatining universallashtirish asosida yuzaga keladi.

Umumjahon xususiyatlarga ega bo'lgan tilga avvallari sobiq ittifoq mamlakatlari uchun davlat tili bo'lgan va MDH davlatlarida xalqaro muloqot tili sifatida o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmagan rus tili ham kiradi. O'zbekiston ommaviy axborot vositalarida rus tilining faoliyat ko'rsatish hajmi ham shundan dalolat beradi. Xususan, tele va radiokanallarda, bosma nashrlarda, shuningdek, internetda o'zbek tili bilan bir qatorda rus tiliga ham katta til maydoni berilgan.

Shunday qilib, eshittirishlar hajmi televideniya: o'zbek tilida – 90,9%, rus tilida – 9%, ingliz tilida – 1% (1); radioda: o'zbek tilida – 99%, rus tilida – 12%, ingliz tilida – 5 % (2); internet-kafeda: o'zbek tilida – 5%, rus tilida – 90%, ingliz tilida – 75% [3].

Uch bosqichli makon o'zbek tilining rus tili orqali ingliz tiliga chiqishini o'z ichiga olishi kerak. Shu bilan birga, zamonaviy davrda ko'p hollarda o'zbek tilida so'zlashuvchilar ingliz tilini rus tili orqali o'rganib, o'zlarida har ikki tilning izini, til orqali esa o'z madaniyatlarining izlarini qoldirib ketishmoqda. Shu bilan birga,

o'zbeklar orasida rus tilini chetlab o'tib ingliz tilini asosan to'g'ridan-to'g'ri o'rganayotganlar soni ortib bormoqda. O'zbekcha-inglizcha va inglizcha-o'zbekcha lug'atlar ko'paygani buning dalilidir. Demak, o'zbek-ingliz ikki tilliligining kuchayishi tendentsiyasi bilan bog'liq holda, shuningdek, M.Z. Sadriiddinova o'zbek tilini davlat tili, – deb e'lon qilishdan oldin “uch tilli lug'atlar faqat o'quv mazmuni bo'lishi mumkin, ular ikki tilda bo'lgan va uchinchi tilni akademik fan sifatida o'rganayotgan maktab o'quvchilari va talabalari uchun mo'ljallangan. Masalan: O'zbekistonning ona tilini biladigan talabalari, millatlararo muloqot tilida gapiradi va ingliz tilini o'rganadi” o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotadi [4,110].

Barcha aytilganlardan kelib chiqib, quyidagi xulosalar chiqarish mumkin:

- birinchidan, ikki til o'zbek tili va madaniyatiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi;
- rus va ingliz tillari ingliz tilining ahamiyatini oshirish tendentsiyasi bilan;
- ikkinchidan, xalq ta'limi doirasida til va madaniyatning o'zaro ta'sirini til taraqqiyoti yo'nalishida inson ongida madaniyat sohasidagi barcha harakatlarni ta'minlay oladigan darajada takomillashtirish;
- uchinchidan, globallashuv sharoitida xalqaro muloqotda madaniyatlarning o'zaro aloqalarni takomillashtirishdan maqsad milliy til va madaniy makonda ularning faoliyat yuritishlari manfaati uchun muvozanatni o'rnatishni ta'minlashga qodir bo'lgan shakl va usullarni topishdan iborat bo'lishi kerak. milliy davlat tilini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlarini so'zsiz kuchaytirgan holda tegishli milliy-madaniy hamjamiyat vakillari bo'lgan shaxslar.

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TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTERCULTURAL RELATIONS

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Abstract. *In this paper, the authors discussed the factors of development of intercultural relations in the development of society and expressed their attitude to the work that should be carried out in this direction.*

Keywords: intercultural communication; interaction of language and culture; functions of language and culture; political symbols of interaction of language and culture.

THE EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT LEARNING FOR STUDENTS IN PHILOLOGICAL AND NON-PHILOLOGICAL FIELDS

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Abstract. *The ability to engage in independent learning for students in both philological and non-philological fields not only expands their knowledge base, but also develops critical thinking, creativity, and lifelong learning skills. This article explores effective strategies for organizing independent learning for different student populations.*

Keywords: philological, non-philological, education, student, field.

Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving educational landscape, independent learning has emerged as a crucial component of academic success across various disciplines. For students in both philological and non-philological fields, the ability to engage in self-directed study not only enhances their knowledge base but also fosters critical thinking, creativity, and lifelong learning skills. This article explores effective strategies for organizing independent learning for these diverse student populations.

Understanding Independent Learning

Independent learning refers to the process where students take the initiative to identify their learning needs, set goals, find resources, and evaluate their progress without constant guidance from instructors. This approach is particularly beneficial in higher education, where students are expected to develop autonomy and self-discipline.

Key Strategies for Effective Organization

1. Goal Setting and Planning

Establishing clear, achievable goals is essential for effective independent learning. Students should be encouraged to set specific objectives related to their coursework or personal interests. Utilizing SMART criteria (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound) can help students create structured plans that guide their learning journey.

2. Resource Identification

Both philological and non-philological students must learn to identify and utilize a variety of resources. This includes academic journals, online databases, libraries, and multimedia tools. Instructors can facilitate this process by providing guidance on how to access and evaluate credible sources, as well as recommending specific materials relevant to their fields of study.

3. Time Management

Effective time management is crucial for independent learners. Students should be taught techniques such as prioritizing tasks, creating schedules, and breaking larger projects into manageable parts. Tools like digital calendars and productivity apps can aid in tracking deadlines and maintaining focus.

4. Active Learning Techniques

Encouraging active engagement with the material enhances retention and understanding. Students can employ techniques such as summarizing information, teaching concepts to peers, or applying theories to real-world scenarios. Incorporating reflective practices, such as journaling or peer discussions, can also deepen their comprehension and critical analysis skills.

5. Utilizing Technology

Technology plays a vital role in facilitating independent learning. Online platforms offer access to a wealth of resources, including e-books, online courses, and forums for discussion. Students should be encouraged to leverage educational technologies that support their learning objectives, such as language learning apps for philological students or data analysis software for non-philological students.

6. Feedback Mechanisms

Regular feedback is essential for monitoring progress and making necessary adjustments to learning strategies. Students should be encouraged to seek feedback from peers and instructors. Additionally, self-assessment tools can help learners evaluate their understanding and identify areas for improvement.

7. Creating a Supportive Learning Environment

A conducive learning environment is vital for independent study. Institutions should promote a culture that values self-directed learning by providing access to study spaces, resources, and mentorship programs. Peer study groups can also foster collaboration and motivation among students from different disciplines.

Challenges and Solutions

While independent learning offers numerous benefits, it also presents challenges such as procrastination, lack of motivation, and difficulty in self-assessment. To address these issues:

- Procrastination can be mitigated by setting short-term deadlines and using accountability partners.

- Motivation can be enhanced through the integration of personal interests into the learning process and by recognizing achievements.

- Self-assessment difficulties can be overcome by providing rubrics or guidelines that help students evaluate their work objectively.

Conclusion

The effective organization of independent learning for students in philological and non-philological fields is essential for fostering autonomy and preparing them for future challenges. By implementing structured strategies that encompass goal setting, resource utilization, time management, active learning techniques, technology integration, feedback mechanisms, and supportive environments, educators can significantly enhance the independent learning experience. As students become more adept at managing their own learning processes, they will not only excel academically but also develop skills that are invaluable in their professional lives.

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TALABALAR UCHUN FILOLOGIYA VA NOFILOLOGIK SOHALARNING MUSTAQIL O'QITISHINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH

Boboyor XUSOMIDDINOV

Annotatsiya. *Filologik va nofilologik yo'nalishdagi talabalar uchun mustaqil ta'lim bilan shug'ullanish qobiliyati nafaqat ularning bilim bazasini kengaytiradi, balki tanqidiy fikrlash, ijodkorlik va umrbod ta'lim ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi. Ushbu maqola turli xil talabalar populyatsiyalari uchun mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etishning samarali strategiyalarini o'rganadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: filologik, nofilologik, ta'lim, talaba, yo'nalish.

ТЕХНИКА ОЛИЙ ЎҚУВ ЮРТЛАРИДА ЧЕТ ТИЛИ ТАЪЛИМИДА КАСБГА ЙЎНАЛТИРИЛГАН КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада муаллиф Техника Олий ўқув юртларида талабаларга чет тилларини ўқитишда катта роль ўйнайдиган коммуникатив компетенциянинг барча компонентларини, энг аввало, уларнинг асосида турувчи лингвистик компетенцияни, яъни лексик ва грамматик компетенцияларни шакллантириш масалалари ҳамда уларнинг ечимлари ҳақида ўз қарашларини билдирган.

Калит сўзлар: чет тиллари, коммуникатив компетенция, компонентлар, назарий материаллар, ишчи дастурлар, ўқув қўлланмалар, усуллар.

Кириш

Мамлакатимизда чет тилларини ўрганиш ва ўргатиш давлат сиёсатининг устувор масалаларига айланиб улгургани сир эмас. Бу эса замон талабидир. Замон билан ҳамнафас бўлиш шахснинг камол топишига, қолаверса, жамият тараққиётига ҳам ижобий таъсир кўрсатади.

Чет тили таълимида касбга йўналтирилган компетенцияни шакллантириш жараёни узлуксизлик тамойилига риоя қилган ҳолда босқичма-босқич амалга оширилади, яъни чет тили таянч курси касбга йўналтирилган чет тили курслари учун асос вазифасини бажариши керак бўлади. Чет тили таълимида исталган соҳа бўйича бўлажак мутахассисларни касбга йўналтириб тайёрлашда машғулотларнинг методик таъминоти таркибида нафақат назарий материаллар, ишчи дастурлар, ўқув қўлланмаларни, балки мавзуга мувофиқ аутентик ахборот манбаларни ҳам қамраб олади.

Нагижа ва мулоҳазалар

Бугунги замонавий дунёда шундай вазият юзага келдики, замонавий муҳандис ўз соҳасидаги инновациялар ва истиқболли ишланмаларни фақат мутахассислиги бўйича чет тилини яхши эгаллаган ҳолдагина ўзлаштира оладилар. Статистик маълумотлар замонавий хорижий нашрларнинг фақат 5-7 % игина рус тилига таржима қилинганини, ўзбек тилида эса бу кўрсаткич янада паст эканлигини қайд этиш мумкин. Шу боис бугунги кунда техник йўналишларда айнан мутахассислигига оид чет тилини биладиган, яъни ҳам касбий соҳасини, ҳам соҳавий чет тилини мукамал биладиган замонавий муҳандисларга талаб ва эҳтиёж кундан кунга ортиб бормоқда.

Афсуски, амалдаги узлуксиз таълим тизимида чет тилини ўқитишда касбий-соҳавий таълимнинг ижтимоий-педагогик асослари етарли даражада ишлаб чиқилмаганлиги боис техника йўналишларида бўлажак мутахассисларни ҳам касбий соҳаси, ҳам соҳавий чет тили бўйича компетентли қилиб тайёрлаш ортда қолаётганини таъкидлаш мумкин [1: 5, 57, 67, 74, 82].

И.А. Зимняя таъкидича, ўқув фаолиятини оптималлаштириш ва интенсификация қилиш:

- касбга йўналтирилган чет тили таълими жараёнида лексик материалларни ўзлаштиришнинг барча босқичларида (танишиш, машқ қилиш, қўллаш ва

назорат) когнитив-коммуникатив, шахсга йўналтирилган ва контекстуал-компетнциявий ёндашувларни таянч деб билиш;

- ўқитувчиларнинг методлар ва усуллари танлашга ижодий ёндашувлари чет тилини ўқитиш олдида қўйилган мақсад ва вазифаларни таъминлашга ёрдам беради;

- чет тилини махсус мақсадларда ўқитишда таълим олувчиларнинг индивидуал психологик хусусиятларини ҳисобга олиш;

- таълимнинг замонавий воситаларидан фойдаланиш ва талабаларнинг мустақил ишларини тўғри ташкил этиш.[2: 35]

Кўриниб турибдики, нофилологик йўналишларда, хусусан, техник ОТМларда чет тилларини ўқитишда талабаларда коммуникатив компетенциянинг барча компонентларини, энг аввало, уларнинг асосида турувчи лингвистик компетенцияни, яъни лексик ва грамматик компетенцияларни шакллантириш зарур. Албатта, нофилологик йўналишларда чет тилини ўқитиш махсус мақсадларга, яъни касбга йўналтирилганлик билан фарқланади. Бироқ муайян касбга йўналтирилган чет тили компетенцияси бўлажак мутахассисларга чет мамлакатлар вакиллари билан соҳавий масалалар бўйича ўзаро фикрлашишлари, улар билан самарали мулоқот олиб боришлари учун илм-фан янгиликларини ўқиб-ўзлаштиришлари учун, аввало, чет тилида фикр ифодалаш кўнлма-малакаларига эга бўлишлари шарт. Нофилологик йўналишларда лингвистик кўнлма-малакаларни ривожлантиришда тил ва нутқ материаллари ОТМ йўналишидан келиб чиқиб танлаб олиниши ва касбий-соҳавий лексика билан интеграциялаб қўлланиши кўзда тутилади.

Касбий соҳада қўлланадаган умумий луғат захираси ва муайян ихтисослик доирасидаги асосий маълумот-ахборотларни ифодалаш учун қўлланадиган махсус атамаларни билиш, уларни ўз тилида ва чет тилида мулоқот юритишда тўғри ва ўринли қўллай олиш чет тилидаги касбий

таълимнинг асоси ҳисобланади. Бўлажак мутахассисда касбий тушунчалар ва уларни ифодаловчи лексик бирликлар (сўзлар, иборалар, жумлалар)ни билиш ва касбий нутқий фаолиятида уларни тушуниш ва тўғри қўллаш кўникма-малакалари шакллантирилиши бугунги кун учун долзарб масаладир.

Техника йўналишида таҳсил олувчи талабалар касбга йўналтирилган нутқий фаолиятнинг барча турларини, энг аввало, соҳага доир ишончли маълумотлар манбаси ҳисобланадиган, касбий мулоқот юритиш учун бевосита зарур муҳим соҳавий маълумотлар олса бўладиган ва коммуникатив кўникмаларни ривожлантириш учун мотивация берадиган махсус аутентик адабиётларни ўқиш чет тилидан мутахассислик фанларини яхшироқ ўзлаштиришнинг муҳим воситаси сифатида фойдаланиш имконини беради. [3; 92]

Лексик материалларни танлаш матнлар ва нутқий вазиятларнинг бўлажак мутахассисларнинг касбий қизиқишлари билан бевосита боғлиқ бўлишини тақозо этади, шу боис хорижий тилларни ўқитиш мутахассислик йўналишидан келиб чиқиб муайян тафовутларга эга бўлади.

Бу эса соҳага йўналтирилган матнларни танлашда муайян тамойилларга таяниш кераклигини тақозо этади. Хусусан, техник йўналишдаги ОТМларда инлиз тилини ўқитишда биз касбий-соҳавий матнларни танлашда қуйидаги тамойилларга асосланиш муҳим деб ҳисоблаймиз:

- манбаларнинг аутентиклиги;
- билим ва ахборот бериш;
- таълимга йўналтирилганлик;
- долзарблик;
- тузилманинг мантиқийлиги;
- мавзуга боғлиқлик;
- тизимлилик;

- тил таълимнинг умумтаълим, касбий таълим даражаларига мувофиқлиги.

Хорижий олимлардан Lado R., Palmer H., Redman S., Н.В.Баграмова, В.А.Бухбиндер, В.А.Кондратьева, И.Л. Литвинов, Р.К.Миньяр-Белоручев кабилар чет тили лексикасини ўргатишнинг самарали воситалари ва методларини тадқиқ қилишга алоҳида эътибор қаратишган. Тадқиқот ишларида касбга йўналтирилган лексик компетенцияни шакллантириш жараёнини ташкил этишнинг турли компонентлари ажратилади. Жумладан, О.И. Жданко [4;39] ўз тадқиқот ишида касбга йўналтирилган лексик компетенцияни шакллантириш жараёнини ташкил этишнинг қуйидаги компонентларини кўрсатиб ўтади ва мазкур компонентлар воситасида шакллантирилган компетенцияларни қуйидагича тавсифлайди:

**Касбга йўналтирилган лексик компетенцияни шакллантириш жараёни
компонентлари**

Лингвистик компонент	Психологик компонент	Методик компонент
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1. Лингвистик компетенция – таълимнинг муайян босқичида нофилологик ОТМларда таълим олувчиларнинг нутқий фаолиятларини амалга ошириш мақсадида касбга йўналтирилган лексик бирликлар (сўз ва сўз бирикмалари)ни керакли даражада тўплашни кўзда тутади.

2. Психологик компетенция лингвистик кўникма ва малакаларни шакллантириш муаммолари билан тўғридан тўғри боғлиқ бўлиб, мазмун-моҳиятига кўра, нутқ олдида қўйилган аниқ вазифадан келиб чиқиб чуқур хотира қатламидан зарур сўз (ибора, турғун бирикма) эталонини тезкорлик билан топиш ва уни нутқ занжирига киритиш қобилиятидир. Лексикани ўрганиш мазмунининг психологик компоненти чет тилида лексик кўникма ва

малакаларни шакллантириш ва ривожлантириш муаммоси билан узвий боғлиқ ҳолда фаолият олиб боради.

3. Методологик компетенция эса касбга йўналтирилган лексика устида мустақил ишлаш кўникма ва малакаларини шакллантиришнинг самарали метод ва усулларини аниқлаш ва касбга йўналтирилган лексик компетенцияни шакллантириш жараёнига татбиқ этишдан иборат .[5;48]

Лингвистик компетенциянинг асосий компонентлари лексик ва грамматик компетенциялар бўлиб, **лексик компетенция** – бу инсоннинг сўзнинг контекстдаги маъносини аниқлаш, икки тилдаги (таълим олувчининг она тили ва ўрганаётган тили доирасида) сўз маъноларининг қамрови миқёсини қиёслаш, сўз маъносининг структурасини англаб етиш ва сўз маъносидаги миллий-маданий хусусиятларни ажрата олишдир. Бу қобилият инсоннинг “шахсий нутқий тажрибаси натижасида юзага келадиган лексик билимлар, кўникма ва малакалар асосида” шаклланади (2, с.61).

Маълумки, лексика тил материалларининг ва таълим мазмунининг энг муҳим қисмини ташкил этади. Техник мутахассис соҳасининг вокабуляри – бу маълум бир тилдаги сўз ва сўз бирикмалари йиғиндисидан иборат бўлиб, лексик бирлик деганда фақат сўзгина эмас, турғун бирикмалар ва иборалар ҳам тушунилади. Уларни нутқий мақсадларда тўплаш таълим олувчиларнинг муайян касбий гуруҳи фаолиятида контекстни юзага келтиради ва лингвистик компетенциянинг муайян босқичида лексик компонентни шакллантиришга хизмат қилади.

Сўзни қўллашда муайян сўзни гап таркибида бошқа сўзлар билан боғлашда мазкур сўзларнинг бошқа сўзлар билан боғланиш имкониятларининг типик шакллари билишга таяниш кўзда тутилади. Бу коллокация (collocations) деб аталади. Буни инглиз, рус ва ўзбек тиллари мисолида кўриб чиқамиз: *practical accuracy – фактическая точность – фактик аниқлик;*

practical application – внедрение в практику – тажриба-синовдан ўтказиш, амалиётга татбиқ қилиш ва ҳ.з. [6;41]

Хулоса

Чет тилида лексик кўникмаларни шакллантиришда сўз шакллари парадигмаларини ва маъновий-семантик парадигмаларни ўзаро алмашилиб, тўғри қўлланишини билиш ва ўрганилган лексикани мунтазам фаоллаштириб бориш ва максимал ҳолда ротация қилиб бориш сўзларни мустаҳкам эслаб қолишнинг муҳим омилларидан бирidir. Фаол лексикани мунтазам кўпайтириб бориш янги сўзларни механик эслаб қолиш орқали эмас, балки аввал ўрганилган сўзларни янги контекстларда қўллаш ҳисобига ҳам амалга оширилиши керак. Агар сўз узок вақт ишлатилмаса, яъни нутқда қўлланмаса, у нофаол лексикага айланади. Айнан сўзларнинг қўлланилишидаги ушбу хусусият фаол ва нофаол лексика ўртасидаги чегаранинг ўзгариб туришига, уларнинг ўрин алмашилиб туришига олиб келиши ҳам мумкин.

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FORMATION OF PROFESSION-ORIENTED COMPETENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION IN TECHNICAL HIGHER EDUCATION COUNTRIES

Gulnoza JORAEVA Nasrullaevna

Abstract. *In this article, the author outlined his views on the issues of formation of all components of communicative competence, which play an important role in teaching foreign languages to students of technical universities, primarily language competence based on them. , that is, lexical and grammatical competences and their solutions.*

Keywords: foreign languages, communicative competence, components, theoretical materials, work programs, teaching aids, methodology.

THE TECHNOLOGY OF USING GAMES AND TOYS IN THE PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN AND CREATING A MODERN MEDIA ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the technology of using games and toys in the psychological development of preschool children and the creation of a modern media environment.*

Keywords: psychological development, toys, game technologies, media environment, interactive tools.

Introduction

Games and toys are among the primary tools for the psychological development of preschool children. These tools help shape children's cognitive, social, and emotional abilities. The modern media environment has introduced new technologies into this process, including interactive games and electronic devices. This article examines the role of game and toy utilization technologies, as well as the modern media environment, in the development of children.

Main Part

If the creative abilities of children in preschool educational institutions are developed through innovative games and toys, the new generation of the 21st century will grow into mentally and spiritually mature individuals. They will assimilate their surroundings based on critical and analytical perspectives, broaden their understanding of the world, acquire intellectually advanced knowledge, and develop independent thinking and problem-solving skills. As a result, by the age of 7, children will be well-prepared to enter the general education school system.

The preschool period is a phase of intensive psychological development, which is carried out based on the conditions formed in early childhood. Innovations emerge in various aspects of psychological development, characterized by new qualities and structural features. This process occurs due to several factors, including communication with adults and peers, acquiring knowledge through different forms and types of activities (such as play, creativity, and daily life). Alongside these innovations, complex social-psychological forms develop, which constitute the individual and its structural elements (such as character, interests, and more) through the development of psychophysiological functions. These include communication, cognition, and activity as well as their core components—abilities and interests. At the same time, the personal organization and socialization of the child continue to develop, which is most evident at the psychophysiological level, in cognitive functions, and in psychomotor skills. New psychological functions, or higher levels, are formed, characterized by features that enable children to adapt to social conditions and the demands of life. The preschool age typically spans from 3 to 6-7 years. During this time, the child begins to separate from adults, leading to changes in the social situation. The child steps beyond the boundaries of the family for the first time and enters the adult world, which operates with specific laws and rules. The scope of communication expands: preschool children begin visiting shops, clinics, and interacting with peers—experiences that are crucial for their development.

It is worth noting that the leading type of activity during the preschool years is various forms of play. Specifically, in the 21st century, innovative toys play a significant role in raising a generation heavily reliant on gadgets and smartphones into well-rounded individuals. Intellectual games and modern toys are activity forms used by preschool children to replicate certain aspects of human activity and master the forms of relationships they will practice later. Children achieve this by substituting one object for another, simplifying real actions. At this age, plot-based role-playing games develop particularly well. These games are centered on the role chosen by the child and the actions required to implement that role.

Results

Game Technologies in Children's Psychological Development:

1. Developmental Toys and Activities:

- **Constructive Games:** Building and assembling toys (e.g., LEGO, blocks) enhance children's logical thinking.
- **Role-Playing Games:** Help children understand social roles in society (e.g., roles of doctor, teacher, chef).
- **Emotion-Enhancing Games:** Activities such as playing with kinetic sand or watercolor painting reduce stress and foster imagination.

2. Interactive Technologies:

- Modern gaming technologies improve children's focus and problem-solving skills.
- Virtual reality provides opportunities for children to explore new knowledge visually and kinesthetically.
- Educational processes are organized through games using e-books and multimedia tools.

The Impact of Modern Media Environments on Children's Development:

• Positive Effects:

1. **Accessibility to Information:** Modern technologies provide children with access to a wide range of knowledge.
 2. **Development of Creativity:** Digital technologies expand children's worldview and foster creativity.
 3. **Harmony of Play and Learning:** Interactive platforms offer educational and developmental games.
- **Negative Effects:**
 1. **Reduced Interpersonal Communication:** Excessive time spent with digital devices may decrease social skills.
 2. **Difficulty in Maintaining Attention:** Rapid visual and audio stimuli may make it harder for children to concentrate.
 3. **Reduced Physical Activity:** Overdependence on media environments negatively affects children's physical development.

Recommendations for Integrating Game Technologies and Media Environments:

1. **Balancing Games and Technologies:** Promote the use of developmental toys alongside electronic devices.
2. **Managing Children's Time:** Set limits on screen time to ensure attention is also given to traditional games.
3. **Educational Programs for Parents and Teachers:** Organize training on selecting appropriate media environments and games for children.
4. **Development of Interactive Toys:** Design toys that encourage activity and stimulate creative thinking in children.

Conclusion

The harmony between games, toys, and the modern media environment plays a crucial role in the psychological development of preschool children. Leveraging technologies effectively is essential for fostering children's growth and ensuring their holistic development.

The Impact of Innovative Toys Includes:

Intellectual Development:

• Logic and Problem-Solving:

Modern toys, such as construction sets, puzzles, and logic games, enhance children's logical thinking, problem-solving, and ability to find creative solutions.

• Language and Speech Development:

Interactive toys, musical toys, and storybooks help expand children's vocabulary, improve their speech, and develop listening skills.

• Memory and Concentration:

Through toys, children learn to remember rules, colors, shapes, and numbers, thereby improving their memory and ability to concentrate.

Social Development:

• Collaboration and Communication:

Toys designed for group play teach children how to collaborate, communicate, and develop interpersonal relationships.

• Social Behavior:

Through toys, children learn about social interactions, rules of play, and how to treat others with respect.

Physical Development:

• Motor Skills:

Moving toys and sports equipment improve children's fine and gross motor skills, help them maintain balance, and enhance coordination.

• Healthy Lifestyle:

Sports toys and outdoor play equipment encourage physical activity and foster the development of a healthy lifestyle.

The proper use, time management, and adaptation of pedagogical approaches to meet modern needs are essential.

The impact of recommended innovative toys for preschool children in fostering a well-rounded generation is significant. These toys positively influence children's intellectual, social, physical, and emotional development.

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MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING PSIXOLOGIK RIVOJLANISHIDA O‘YIN VA O‘YINCHOQLARDAN FOYDALANISH TEXNOLOGIYASI

Sitora ASATULLAYEVA Dilmurodovna

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning psixologik rivojlanishi va zamonaviy media muhitini yaratishda o'yinlar va o'yinchoqlardan foydalanish texnologiyasi tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit soʻzlar: psixologik rivojlanish, oʻyinchoqlar, oʻyin texnologiyalari, media muhiti, interaktiv vositalar.

**OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARIDA TIL VA USLUB MASALASI:
TAHLIL, TASNIF, QIYOS
2024.11.30**

**VI Sho'ba: Mediata'limda ijodiy yondoshuv. til va uslub
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